

Theoretische Grundlagen zur Strukturverbesserung der regionalen Wirtschaft im Kontext der Digitalität

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Abstrakt: Dieser Artikel untersucht die theoretischen Grundlagen der digitalen
Ökonomie, regionale Ökonomien, strukturelle Veränderungen und die Verbesserung der
Struktur regionaler Ökonomien.

Schlüsselwörter: Digitalisierung; digitale Wirtschaft; regionale Wirtschaft;
regionale Wirtschaftsstruktur; strukturelle Veränderungen; regionales
Wirtschaftssystem.

Theoretical fundamentals of improving the structure of the regional economy in the context of digitality

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Abstract. This article examines the theoretical foundations of the digital
economy, regional economies, structural changes, and improving the structure of
regional economies.

Key words: digitization; digital economy; regional economy; regional economic
structure; structural changes; regional economic system.

Introduction.

One of the current trends in the development of the world economy is the process
of digitization. Ensuring economic independence and security in the digital space is a
priority for the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Ensuring the necessary independence in the digital space, creating a modern, i.e.
new digital ecosystem in the country, its full protection is a matter of national security.
In addition, it is necessary to maintain a balance of interests and ensure the protection
of information, both at the state level and with the use of modern devices, in relation
to any individual.

The process of digitization covers all sectors of the economy and requires a
sufficient change in its composition. In our opinion, it is necessary not only to ensure
the growth of the country's economy, but also to give it a radically new content, an
innovative character.

In the current uncertainty in the world, the importance of regional economic
development is growing. Economic growth in developed and developing countries is

mainly achieved through the effective use of local natural and economic potential and improving the structural structure of the regional economy. Therefore, the structural transformation of the regional economy is becoming a key factor in ensuring economic growth in foreign countries.

In world practice, extensive research is being conducted to study and solve the problems of improving the structure of regional economies. In particular, special attention is paid to the modernization and diversification of the region's economy, the improvement of methods of distribution, analysis and forecasting, taking into account the specific characteristics of the factors of production.

Accelerated development of industry and services through radical structural changes and a sharp increase in their share in GDP are among the priorities in ensuring sustainable economic growth in Uzbekistan. The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 addresses the issue of "expanding the scale of modernization and diversification of regional economies, rapid development of relatively low-growth districts and cities, primarily by increasing industrial and export potential." In particular, the share of industry in the regional economy remains relatively low. Given this situation, one of the priorities is to improve the structure of the regional economy based on local conditions and existing potential.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. PP-3182 of August 8, 2017 "On priority measures to ensure rapid socio-economic development of the regions" Resolution No. PQ-4102 of January 8, 2019 "On additional measures to further improve the activities of sectors for integrated socio-economic development of the regions", Resolution No. PP-4699 of April 28, 2020 "On the widespread introduction of digital economy and e-government" Resolution of the Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 1, 2020 No PP-4702 "On the introduction of a rating system of socio-economic development of the regions" and other regulations related to the integrated development of the regions issues.

Analysis of literature.

In the practice of many developed countries, the problem of identifying areas that will contribute to the modernization of the national economy and the implementation of structural changes in it is studied not only at the macro and micro levels, but also at the regional level. Solving problems related to the regulation of the regional economy requires their scientific and methodological substantiation and in-depth analysis.

Kadyrov et al. estimated the impact of investments in ICT fix assets, number of Internet users and number of mobile subscribers on volume of ICT services in Uzbekistan and had shown the number of Internet users is the strongest factor of volume of ICT services.

Structural changes are a complex and continuous process that is manifested not only by quantitative changes, but also by qualitative changes. Structural changes take place at different levels of the economic system: at the individual or household level - at the nano level, at the enterprise or firm level - at the micro level, at the sectoral or

regional level - at the meso level, at the national or global economy level - at the macro level and are classified as follows (Picture 1).

Macro level	Mezo level	Micro level	Nano level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in the ratio between aggregate demand and its elements at the national level, changes in the composition of GDP and other macroeconomic indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in GRP and its elements at the regional level, changes in the share of GRP in the network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in the appearance and types of products at the enterprise or firm level and the share of product types in the gross income of the enterprise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in consumption and income at the individual and household level, increase in specific demand, change in the share of savings in income, changes in the structure of consumption

Picture 1. Description of the scale of structural changes*

*Developed by the author

The concepts of structural change have been studied in depth by economists, including the Austrian scientist J. Schumpeter “The main driving force of the economic system is the renewal of the structure of consumption, the application of new methods of production and supply of goods, the improvement of markets and the use of modern forms of economic organization”[1], he emphasizes.

In scientific theories on the implementation of structural changes in the regional economy, scientists have focused on the location of productive forces in more regions. In particular, I. Tunen's theory of "agricultural standard", A. Weber's [2] The theory of "industrial standards", the theory of "placement", F. Perruning [3] Theories of “growth poles and center of development” are important theories in this regard. Also W.Crystaller [4] On the basis of the "theory of the central place" the issues of effective structures of the regions, rational directions of movement of goods and services, the formation of a favorable structure of regional administration are covered.

The study of foreign experience of structural changes allows us to follow the main trends in the world, identify ways to implement the strategy of structural renewal of the country, region and industry, the priorities of change in production, technology and management of regional enterprises.

Structural change policies in developed countries include efforts to redistribute resources to lay the foundations for economic growth and qualitatively renew it. This is done through the formation of regulatory approaches to ensure the transfer of resources and capital to priority sectors aimed at restructuring the industry, directing resources and investment to locomotive industries that benefit from non-profit activities.

Additional sources of raw materials, electricity, production capacity, labor resources, etc. will be required to make structural changes. International experience shows that in the system of international division of labor, developed countries have a practice of exporting environmentally harmful industries that require a lot of labor and resources. In addition, as part of technological reconstruction, obsolete equipment will

be exported or replaced with modern ones. Therefore, investment projects will focus on the use of advanced technologies.

Each region of our country is unique. The possibilities of districts within a province are also not the same. Therefore, the issues of economic development of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the city of Tashkent and the regions are being discussed separately. The head of our state pays great attention to the relevance and practicality of the planned measures. It is criticized that the leaders of the center are satisfied with the general reports of the governors in decision-making, and from now on each issue of the region should be resolved at the district, village, mahalla, branch and enterprise level. It is necessary to start the development of programs in each village, to specify in which village to develop, in what direction, how much money should be allocated for this [5].

Based on the above, structural changes in the region should be made by diverting resources from one sector to another within the existing potential in the region.

Each region should not only specialize in specific products, but also take a comprehensive approach to the development of all sectors of the economy to ensure normal production conditions and the lives of the people of the region. The optimal, most efficient and balanced development of individual sectors of the regional economy with the specialization of production given to it implies the complexity of the development of the regional economy. The specialization and integrated development of the region's economy is aimed at increasing the region's contribution to the country's economy and ensuring that the needs of the region's population are met.

The integrated development of the regions includes the provision of the most rational network and regional ratios, the establishment and maintenance of a mutually optimal ratio, including:

- specialization and ancillary industries, as well as service sectors;
- mining and manufacturing industry;
- light and heavy industry;
- industry and agriculture;
- industrial and social infrastructure;
- manufacturing and services.

The analysis of the sectoral structure of the economy of the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan on industrial specialization can be divided into several groups [6]:

1. Energy producing regions:

- fuel and energy - Kashkadarya, Fergana, Bukhara;
- electricity, lighting, food - Syrdarya;
- fuel, electricity, non-ferrous metallurgy, construction materials - Tashkent.

2. Energy-consuming regions with developed diversified industries:

- non-ferrous metallurgy, chemical, electric power industry, construction materials - Navoi;
- food, machinery, construction materials, printing - Tashkent;
- machinery, food, light industry - Andijan.

3. Leading industries - regions with light and food industries:

- light and food industry, electricity – the Republic of Karakalpakstan;
- food industry - Samarkand;
- light food products in the industrial structure according to the localization coefficient - Namangan, Khorezm, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh.

The territorial structure of the economy is an aggregate expression of a single developing system (region) that unites all the sectors operating in its territory and determines the specialization of the region as a whole.

The research methodology consists of a set of methods of comparative, structural, functional and statistical analysis, a system approach, monographs survey, expert estimates, etc. In addition to quantitative analysis, a method of sociological surveys of participants of leasing relationships are used while the research.

Analysis and results.

The most important and generalizing indicator of the regional structure is the gross regional product, which characterizes the socio-economic development of the region, and includes the main components such as industry, construction, agriculture, trade turnover, services. These indicators are mainly structural determinants that characterize the economic system of the region at the micro and macro levels.

The territorial structure of the economy is effective only if it ensures the sustainable and efficient development of the region and its industries, the rational use of natural resources and economic potential, the improvement of living standards.

Qualitative expression of these trends are regional shifts in the economy, which characterize the positive or negative mechanisms of regional development.

The study of the quantitative characteristics of regional structural changes in the economy uses the cost and exact indicators of gross regional product (GRP); growth rates, estimates per capita and assessment of their indices; the ratio of cost and net performance in the dynamics over a number of years is determined. Quantitative changes in the regional economy can be defined as follows [7]:

$$C_c = D_1 - D_0, \text{ in where,}$$

C_c - relative expression of structural changes in the economy;

D_1 and D_0 - are the share of the structural indicators in the current and base period, respectively.

However, the index method of structural shifts, expressed in percentages or percentages, is widely used; as the ratio of the share of the component indicator in the current and base periods, it indicates how much the value of the component indicator share has increased or decreased in a given period.

This complex indicator characterizes the deep processes of structural change in the economy.

$$L = D_1/D_0, \text{ in where,}$$

L - structural change index;

D_1 and D_0 - the share of structural indicators in the current and base period, respectively.

The structure of the economy at the regional level will be effective if: the growth rates of GRP and other fundamental sectors that make up this indicator will increase;

increasing the share of industries that require production and high-tech knowledge in the regions, increasing the share of exports and reducing imports and, accordingly, the formation of an optimal structure of the regional economy, their natural and economic potential.

In turn, in modern global processes, competition extends and intensifies at all levels of economic relations. Regions will not only begin to participate in interregional competition in the national economy, but will also enter global competitive processes. Competitiveness will become the most important support of the regional economy, the goal of regional policy and the condition for the preservation and development of regions, which requires a new regional paradigm (model). At the same time, it is important to improve the structure of the regional economy and its adaptation to the new reality. (Picture 2).

Picture 2. Territorial structure*

*Developed by the author

In this regard, the region can be seen as an economic entity that must prove its right to a share in the economic wealth of a country with economic success, which means a transition from redistributive principles of regional policy to stimulating endogenous factors of development.

Regional competitiveness is a function of interregional competition. The development of globalization processes, the manifestation of their negative and

positive consequences, as well as the formation of a "digital economy" allow us to talk about increasing the independence of regions and their role in the development of the national economy.

In addition, the role of the regional economic system in improving the structure of the regional economy is great, of course. In our opinion, the economic system of a region is a complex that includes the interrelationships of specific economic, social and natural environmental factors and the interrelationships between their internal elements.

There are two different approaches to the concept of sustainable development of the economic system, firstly, it is to support a certain level of any final economic indicators, and secondly, to achieve the highest levels of economic growth indicators.

Sustainable development of the economic system is a fundamental economic concept Sustainable development is the constant maintenance of key socio-economic and environmental indicators of the economic system.

Sustainability is based on economic equilibrium, which is an important condition for the effective functioning and development of any economic system. In particular, the achievement of market equilibrium of supply and demand depends on many factors, but should.

The following conclusions can be drawn about the possibility of achieving the goals set for the sustainable development of the economic system of the region:

formation of the process of interaction with the environment, which allows to earn-out production without harmful effects on the environment;

creation of conditions for balance between the economy and the social sphere, which allows the use of the results of economic activity in order to increase the level of social development;

implementation of mechanisms for sustainable development of the economic system of the region, aimed at the interests of future and present generations.

The following special principles based on the concept of sustainable development can be distinguished in the research conducted to determine the principles of sustainable development of the regional economic system:

the principle of taking into account the interdependent development of the elements of the economic system of the region, in the observance of the balance of development between the elements that reflect the necessity and importance of interaction with the social, economic, environmental, external environment;

the principle of achieving sustainable development dynamics in various areas of the regional economic system, including achieving economic results, efficiency in foreign economic activity, increasing social stability, environmental security, determining the number of indicators representing the required level of sustainable development in the regional economic system and its subsystems;

the principle of priority of end goals, characterized by the emergence of resources that ensure the sustainable development of the economic system of the region.

Today, any socio-economic system, including the regional economic system, seeks leadership in sustainable development by meeting the needs of all stakeholders,

adhering to specific principles. The economic system of a sustainable developing region must adhere to the following principles:

support and respect for the rights of the population;

use of natural resources on the basis of minimal damage to the environment, while preserving the diversity of habitats;

identification and mitigation of economic, environmental and social risks and impacts;

open and real relations with stakeholders, taking into account their views and interests in decision-making;

increase the profitability and efficiency of the regional economic system;

to establish relations on the basis of international business practices and ethical norms created in the world market;

timely informing various stakeholders about the activities of the regional economic system.

Structural changes in the regional economy may be different (Picture 3).

Picture 3. Types of structural changes in the regional economy*

*Developed by the author

Chaotic structural changes are a type of structural change that is not a strategic vector of planned change. this type of structural change is often spontaneous, through contradictory measures. This will not lead to the growth of the regional economy.

The administrative type of structural change in the regional economy can be understood as a type in which the initiative comes from the state authorities, when changes are established "from above". According to S.V. Doholyan, structural changes occur due to the merger or cooperation of decisions made by the state. The management of companies is only the executor of government decisions, is not responsible for their consequences and does not risk their resources, so they do not always lead to increased efficiency of enterprises[8].

Market type is a structural change based on the internal motivation of the business community formed under the influence of external stimuli from government agencies.

In our opinion, the most acceptable of all the types of structural changes mentioned above are the market and administrative types.

It should be noted that today, administrative and market-type changes cannot take place without the participation of all groups of stakeholders in regional development. All stakeholder groups (local government, business, research institutes, educational institutions, trade unions and the population) have a certain influence on the process of structural change in the economy, but the greatest influence comes from scientific and educational institutions, which can be explained by their willingness to digitize the economy.

The main methods of stimulating innovative activity at the regional level: administrative, economic and spiritual (Picture 4).

Picture 4. Basic methods of stimulating innovative activity*

*Developed by the author

In our opinion, the structural structure of the regional economy cannot be improved only on the basis of the motivation of stakeholder groups. The system of incentive methods should be part of the overall mechanism of structural restructuring of the regional economy.

According to S.I. Ozhegova, “a mechanism is a system, a device that determines the order of certain types of activity” [9].

According to M.K. Fayzullov, “the mechanism of structural changes in the regions should be based primarily on the formation and strengthening of the role of regional management of innovation processes” [10].

In our view, the mechanism of structural change of the regional economy can be presented as follows (Picture 5).

Picture 5. The mechanism of structural change in the regional economy*

*Developed by the author

Territorial power, which forms the institutional environment for changing the structure of the regional economy, can be called the “management center” of the mechanism.

In our opinion, the subjects of the mechanism are the stakeholders of regional development, ie regional governments, scientific organizations, educational institutions, the business community, the population of the region. Subjects should be in constant interaction. The object of the mechanism is the structure of the regional economy. As a goal, we can increase the efficiency of the structure of the regional economy and improve the quality of life and living standards of the population of the regions.

The methods of subject exposure include:

- socio-economic;
- institutional;
- innovative;
- adaptive;
- investment projects;
- organizational, etc.

This mechanism is not static, but focused on continuous improvement. At the same time, it is important to develop an innovation incentive system for stakeholder groups within the proposed mechanism.

The development of the economic system of the regions requires, first of all, the identification of current and future requirements, the development of multivariate scenario forecasts to meet current and future needs.

It is necessary to form a new mechanism by identifying the priorities by forecasting the needs and requirements of the population of the region and the economic entities operating there.

In the sustainable development of the regional economic system:

private enterprises;

state enterprises;

state non-profit organizations;

it is expedient to assess the share of non-governmental non-profit organizations in GRP.

Given the changes in GRP under the influence of external and internal factors, the creation of new financial institutions and the improvement of existing ones will create the basis for sustainable development of the economic system of the region.

Improving the structure of the regional economy in the context of digitalization Regional development requires the active participation of all stakeholders, restructuring should be based on the use of administrative and market forms and structural changes in the regional economy, resulting in improving the efficiency of the regional economy and living standards.

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